

A stepwise approach to search for illicit connections in the storm sewers of Berlin: using EC and DTS

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Highlights

- The Berlin Fennsee is suffering from surface water quality issues probably related to illicit connections to storm sewers in the area.
- In a stepwise approach, a network of electrical conductivity (EC) sensors was first deployed to identify hotspot areas that likely contain illicit connections.
- In a second step, Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) was used in one hotspot area to identify the exact location of an illicit connection with multiple discharges per day.

Introduction

Illicit connections to storm sewers have a negative impact on surface water quality in Berlin. To improve water quality in the city, the Berliner Wasserbetriebe intends to locate and eliminate these illicit connections. The current approach using visual and CCTV inspection to pinpoint the exact locations of illicit discharges has proven insufficient: only a limited number of wrong connections have been found this way over the last years.

To support utilities in obtaining a cost-effective approach for the search of illicit connections, a stepwise approach has been developed and tested in a storm sewer in Berlin as part of the DWC research project (digital-water.city). This paper presents the approach and the obtained results.

Materials and methods

The study area is the Fennsee area in Charlottenburg, Berlin. The Fennsee is a small urban lake with major water pollution issues that are suspected to be related to illicit connections to the contributing storm sewers. The entire stormwater catchment has an area of 220 ha, a sewer length of 39 km, around 800 manholes and approximately 1500 house connections.

As a first step, storm sewers were investigated using a network of sensors for electrical conductivity (EC) as 'hotspot' screening, see Figure 1. With a difference in typical EC values between urban stormwater runoff (~ 200 µS/cm) and sanitary sewage (> 600 µS/cm) illicit connections in the upstream sub-catchment are suspected when measuring high EC values (Launay et al., 2016). Often, these high values are measured intermittently, in correspondence with intermittent wastewater flows from illicit connections.

Using a set of six EC sensors, we identified hotspots using a downstream-to-upstream approach, relocating sensors every four weeks. Based on a sewer network analysis, the sensors were strategically positioned such that the catchment areas were divided in multiple sub-catchments. Areas with 'positive' results were subsequently further divided into smaller sub-sub-catchments, et cetera. The EC sensors were installed inside manholes, creating sufficient water depth at invert level

to guarantee submerged sensors (using small sandbags). Costs for the EC sensor network added to approximately EUR 4.000 per monitoring period of four weeks.

As the second step, we searched for the exact locations of illicit connections within a selected hot-spot area using Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS). DTS is a proven method to find and locate illicit connections in storm sewers (e.g. Hoes et al., 2009; Schilperoort et al., 2013). We used two fibre-optic cables (1.200 and 1.800 m, see Figure 2) as 'long temperature sensors' that monitored in-sewer temperatures over a sewer section of roughly 1.450m for five continuous weeks (22 September - 28 October, 2021) at a 1-minute interval. The additional cable length was needed due to a decentral location of the DTS unit (selected for its good access to the sewer system) and due to two cable loops in *cul-de-sac* streets. For localization of the cables in the sewer, we placed ice packs on top of the fibre-optic cables at selected manholes. This way, the position of these manholes were identified in the datasets, giving a reference for the localization of illicit connections. Prior to analysis, the data collected during these tests were excluded from the datasets, as well as any data collected during rainfall. The latter exclusion is needed as inflowing storm water greatly influences in-sewer temperatures.

Illicit connections were identified scanning the remaining temperature datasets for locations that show relatively high temperatures with a sudden and intermittent character. These sudden temperature increases are often caused by spills of warm wastewater into the storm sewer, for instance from a wrongly connected shower or laundry machine. Costs for the application of DTS range between EUR 10-20 per m¹ of sewer pipe (or EUR 60-100 per household).

Figure 1. Hotspots (red ovals on the map on the right) identified using EC monitoring. On the left, two examples of monitoring results showing EC values (in green) and precipitation (in blue). The top left graph shows frequent peaks in EC values associated with a hotspot area; the lower left graph does not show any EC peaks in dry weather situations. Green, yellow and red stars on the map indicate all monitoring locations of EC sensors.

Results

For the EC monitoring an evaluation method with a traffic light system was developed indicating the probability of the presence of illicit connections in the upstream area. First, all data associated with storm events was removed from the dataset as the inflow of storm water can cause large variations in the EC signal (peaks related to runoff from streets and roofs, and subsequent dilution processes). Then, differentiation in dry weather data was done counting the amount of relevant EC peaks ($>600 \mu\text{S/cm}$) in the four week period: more than four peaks gave a strong indication of illicit connections (red flag), two to four peaks a medium indication (yellow) and no or only one peak a weak indication (green). In addition, one very high peak larger than $4.000 \mu\text{S/cm}$ also counted as a strong indication of illicit connections. This way, ten hotspot areas (red ovals) were identified, see Figure 1. Also, for 16.5 km sewer length the presence of illicit connection was considered 'unlikely'.

The DTS monitoring results in the hotspot area revealed one illicit connection (see Figure 2). At that location in the storm sewer inflows were observed on 55 occasions in the five-week period, indicating an average of about two spills per day. Typically, the first spill began early in the morning (around 06h00), except for the weekend (08h00-10h00). The number of discharges as well as the observed pattern correspond well to a typical household pattern. The illicit connection has been confirmed in the field by inspection of the stormwater house connection in cooperation with the caretaker of the building. During dry weather conditions a small water flow and residues of sanitary sewage have been located in the storm water maintenance chamber of the building. Additionally, at a few other locations incidental temperature variations were detected. These anomalies were however not suspected to be related to illicit connections, but rather to spills of (waste)water through gully pots. At one location, for instance, the temperature variation was observed directly next to a flower shop around closing time of the shop. These locations have not been further studied in the field.

Figure 2. The routing of two fibre-optic cables (green: 1.200m; red: 1.800m) in a hotspot area (right bottom), both connected to a DTS unit installed in a small container on top of a manhole cover (right top). The graph on the left shows the monitoring results for 4 days (30 September – 4 October, vertical axis) over a length of approximately 100 m of cable length. The illicit connection at $x = 817$ is recognized by sudden and intermittent high temperatures at that location and that subsequently move downstream (from right to left in this graph).

Discussion and conclusions

Using EC and DTS monitoring in the storm sewer network of the Berlin Fennsee catchment area, several hotspot areas have been identified as well as one illicit connection exactly pinpointed in a selected hotspot area. With these results, this approach has proven more effective than earlier trials in the same area when no illicit connections were found using visual and CCTV inspection.

The application of EC sensors in a sewer network is relatively straightforward and generally associated with limited costs. The main drawback is that the installation of sensors is limited to manholes, meaning that any illicit connections in-between manholes cannot be exactly pinpointed. Furthermore, conditions in the sewer system strongly determine to what extent a wastewater spill from an illicit connection is observed by a downstream EC sensor. For instance, a wastewater spill could be diluted by groundwater infiltration resulting in much lower EC values (and hence a non-detect). Also, the method is less suitable for (partly) submerged storm sewers due to the large volume of water stored in the system also resulting in the ‘flattening’ of the EC peaks.

The use of DTS also has its advantages and drawbacks. The main advantage of the technique is that it can pinpoint illicit connections to the exact location in the sewer. The main drawback is the relatively large effort (and hence costs) associated with the technique. The need for sophisticated equipment, installation of fibre-optic cables in the sewer, and specialized data analysis contribute to these costs. As a result, the application of DTS in storm sewer of the entire Fennsee area (39 km) was considered too expensive.

The approach as used in the Fennsee area in Berlin combines the advantages of both techniques: a relatively low costs search for hotspot areas followed by exact pinpointing of illicit connections only where needed.

An important aspect of the presented approach is the choice when to switch from using the EC sensor network to using the DTS technology for further investigations. In other words: at which size of a hotspot area is the area not further split up in smaller sub-catchments by relocating the EC sensors, but is the complete area investigated using DTS? Based on the experience in Berlin and other locations we recommend a maximum size of a hotspot area of 1-3 km of sewer length. The rationale behind this is that a significant share of the costs for a DTS monitoring project are fixed costs (rental of equipment, data processing and analysis) that are not dependent on the length of the applied fibre-optic cables. Hence, using DTS to monitor only 50 meters of sewer section in-between two manholes would be very cost-ineffective. Monitoring sewer length (much) larger than 3 km would require top-end DTS units, which would further increase project costs.

The case study in the Fennsee area was the first application of the presented two-step approach to search for illicit connections. In future, the approach will be further used and developed in other catchments in Berlin that are under the suspicion of illicit connections.

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